

NDAC/LO/011

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WP1100: Preprocessing of SM Data (Definition)

by L Lindegren

1. Principles

The preprocessing of Star Mapper (SM) data shall determine the transit times of the programme stars, i.e. the instants at which they cross an imaginary reference line in the SM field of view. The reference line is defined by some given functional relation between the field coordinates (η , ζ , f). It should nominally coincide, for each value of ζ , with the average η -coordinate of the slit centres (Fig. 1); this will minimize the influence of attitude rate errors on the transit times.

Depending on the scanning velocity, as given by the Real Time Attitude, a matched numerical filter is set up through which the SM counts are fed. The interpolated maximum of the filter output gives the transit time.

FIGURE 1. Example of the nominal position of the reference line (dashed) on a non-periodic SM grid, and how to define the u -coordinate of a star.

2. Summary of I/O Data

The relevant Data Interface Descriptions (DID's) are:

DID#	SOURCE	DATA INPUT TO SM PREPROCESSING
19	SM Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • header • count records
20	RT Attitude	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • attitude angles
21	Star Catalogue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • photometric data, multiplicity
DID#	DESTINATION	DATA OUTPUT FROM SM PREPROCESSING
22	Attitude Reconstitution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • transit time

2.1. SM Data format

On account of TYCHO, a continuous stream of SM data is transmitted from the satellite. We shall assume, however, that only short stretches corresponding to the expected transits of bright ($B < 11?$) HIPPARCOS stars are forwarded to NDAC for the main mission analysis. The required length of these stretches depends on the slit pattern, scanning speed, sampling frequency, and uncertainties of the Real Time (RT) attitude and star positions. For the pattern in Fig. 1, and assuming 1.5 as rms error in both RT attitude and star positions, the minimum length would correspond to about 54 as, or 180 samples at 600 Hz and $v = 180$ as/s. The two photometric channels (B_T and V_T) should be given separately (not $B_T + V_T$), although the samples may be interleaved.

Thus we envisage the SM data for one transit to consist of

- a header identifying the star, SM index, field index, and the time of (say) the first sample; and
- two count records, each about 180 bytes, containing the photometric samples of the two channels (compressed form).

The extracted stretches comprise less than 5 % of the complete SM records. The header should be less than 16 bytes.

2.2. Real Time attitude format

On-board the satellite, the attitude is probably represented by three Euler angles (ϕ, θ, ψ) , giving the orientation w.r.t. the nominal scanning law, and their derivatives $(\dot{\phi}, \dot{\theta}, \dot{\psi})$. The attitude estimate is regularly updated, with a fixed frequency of the order of 1 Hz. The RT attitude supplied to us may therefore consist of the estimated state vector $(\phi \ \theta \ \psi \ \dot{\phi} \ \dot{\theta} \ \dot{\psi})'$ at the same instants, and the nominal attitude (which may be an analytical expression covering a longer time interval).

Since such data are easily converted to absolute attitude angles and derivatives $(\alpha_z, \delta_z, \omega, \dot{\alpha}_z, \dot{\delta}_z, \dot{\omega})$, and if necessary interpolated to the frame mid-times, we may assume that the RT attitude is available in this "canonical" form.

3. Method and Basic Equations

The count records will be fed through a numerical filter which resembles the expected signal shape ($\approx$ cross-correlation). Heuristically, the filter can be derived as follows.

Consider a Poisson process with continuous intensity (= expected count rate in Hz) of the form

$$I(t; a, b, \tau) = b + a S[(t - \tau)\dot{u}] \quad (1)$$

$S(u)$ is the known response of the slit system to a star at position u (measured from the reference line along $+\eta$), and a, b, τ are unknown parameters (background, star intensity, transit time). The (effective) scanning speed $\dot{u}$ is assumed constant and known. Let $n(t), t_0 \leq t < T$, be the accumulated number of counts from t_0 to t . The sample-function density of this counting process is

$$p\{n(t), t_0 \leq t < T \mid a, b, \tau\} =$$

$$= \exp \left[- \int_{t_0}^T I(t; a, b, \tau) dt + \int_{t_0}^T \ln[I(t; a, b, \tau)] dn(t) \right] \quad (2)$$

The likelihood of (a, b, τ) , for given $n(t)$, is the logarithm of (2). Assuming that the interval $[t_0, T[$ is wide enough to support $S[(t-\tau)\dot{u}]$, we find the likelihood function

$$\ell(a, b, \tau) = \ell_0(a, b) + \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \ln[1 + qS[(t-\tau)\dot{u}]] dn(t) \quad (3)$$

where $q = a/b$. This is clearly a convolution of the comb function $dn(t)$ with the continuous filter function $\ln[1 + qS(t\dot{u})]$. Thus, for given a and b, the Maximum Likelihood estimate of τ is simply the point at which the filtered signal [integral in (3)] is maximized.

In the actual case we do not know $n(t)$ but only the incremental counts over fixed intervals of length $\Delta t^* = t_k - t_{k-1}$:

$$N_k^* = n(t_k) - n(t_{k-1}) \quad (4)$$

The integral may then be replaced by the sum

$$J(\tau) = c \Delta t^* \sum_k \ln[1 + qS[(t_k - \frac{1}{2}\Delta t^* - \tau)\dot{u}]] N_k^* \quad (5)$$

where c is an arbitrary positive constant.

A different filter was proposed in Annex A, eqn (A.7.11). This was however primarily optimized for determining the star intensity (a), and was therefore balanced (integrated filter area = 0). In contrast, the filter in (5) is clearly unbalanced, since $\ln[1 + qS] \geq 0$; but since it is in fact optimum for determining τ it should be preferred for the SM preprocessing. The photometric parameters a and b may still be determined (suboptimally), e.g. as follows. At the maximum ($\tau = \hat{\tau}$) we have

$$E[J(\hat{\tau})] \approx E[J(\tau_{\text{true}})] = \alpha_0 a + \beta_0 b \quad (6)$$

with the known coefficients

$$\alpha_0 = (c/\dot{u}) \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \ln[1 + qS(u)] S(u) du \quad (7a)$$

$$\beta_0 = (c/\dot{u}) \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \ln[1 + qS(u)] du \quad (7b)$$

At some distance (w samples) away from the maximum, we have similarly

$$E[J(\hat{\tau} \pm w\Delta t^*)] \approx \alpha_{\pm w} a + \beta_{\pm w} b \quad (8)$$

with easily computable $\alpha_{\pm w}$, $\beta_{\pm w}$. From (6) and (8) we can thus obtain estimates of a and b as linear combinations of J_{max} and the J -value at some other point.

It is seen that the discrete filter coefficients

$$f_j = c \Delta t^* \ln[1 + qS[(j-\frac{1}{2})\Delta t^* \dot{u}]] \quad (9)$$

depend on $q = a/b$ and $\dot{u}$. Strict ML estimation of τ thus requires iteration: e.g. start with some a priori q -value, compute filter output $\{J_k\}$, determine τ , a , b and hence q ; etc. It may however be sufficient to use a fixed q -value, e.g. corresponding to the faint limit; the statistical loss compared to using the optimal q is probably quite small.

It may be more important to take into account the deviation of $\dot{u}$ from its nominal value ($v = 180$ as/s). If the reference line is given by the equation $\eta = \eta_{fg}(\zeta)$ (cf. Annex A, p. 14), we have for a star at (η, ζ, f) :

$$u(t) = \eta - \eta_{fg}(\zeta) \quad (10)$$

and hence

$$\dot{u} = \dot{\eta} \cdot \eta_{fg}^{-1}(\zeta) \dot{\zeta} \quad (11)$$

[with $\eta_{fg}^{-1} \equiv (d/d\zeta)\eta_{fg}$]. Using (A.9.17), (A.3.4), and $\dot{\underline{x}} = \underline{T}'\underline{\omega}$, we get

$$\dot{u} = - \underline{B}_{fg}(\zeta) \underline{D}(\alpha_z, \delta_z, \omega) \begin{pmatrix} \dot{\alpha}_z \\ \dot{\delta}_z \\ \dot{\omega} \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The (1,3)-matrix $\underline{B}_{fg}$ is defined in (A.9.18) [where the right member should be transposed]. It can be noted that the (1,3)-matrix $\underline{B}_{fg}\underline{D}$ is also used in the Attitude Reconstitution [see NDAC/LO/006, eqn (44)], so it should be output from the SM Pre-processing.

Note also that $\dot{u}$ may be positive or negative depending on the sense of rotation (while its absolute value is constant within $\pm 2\%$). In the nominal scanning mode the spin axis is parallel to $+z$; hence $\dot{\omega} > 0$, $\dot{\eta} < 0$, and $\dot{u} < 0$. The software should be able to handle both senses.

The filter coefficients f_j may be computed and stored for a range of $\dot{u}$ -values, from which the most appropriate set is then selected for a given transit. If the filter is realized as a 'folded filter' (Lindgren 82-03-03, 82-03-23, 82-04-06), only the long filter (corresponding to the slit positions) need to be adjusted; the short filter (corresponding to the single-slit light curve) may be constant.

Thus, if u_n ($n = 1$ to NSLIT) are the u -coordinates of the slit centres, we define the integers

$$k_n = \text{NINT}[u_n / (\dot{u}\Delta t^*)] \quad (13)$$

and find that

$$f_{j+k_1} \approx f_{j+k_2} \approx \dots \approx f_{j+k_{\text{NSLIT}}} \approx f_j \quad (14)$$

so that the filter output is approximated by

$$J(t_0 + j\Delta t^*) \approx J_j = \underbrace{\sum_{m=-M}^M F_m}_{\text{'short' filter}} \underbrace{\sum_{n=1}^{\text{NSLIT}} N_n^*}_{\text{'long' filter}} e^{k_n^* + m - j} \quad (15)$$

The length of the short filter $(2M+1)$ depends on the width of the single-slit response function, $S_0(u - u_n)$. For $1/\Delta t^* = 600$ Hz we may have $M \sim 6$. Putting

$$F_m = c \Delta t^* \ln[1 + q S_0(m\Omega\Delta t^*)] \quad (16)$$

where $\Omega = \langle |\dot{u}| \rangle$ is the nominal scanning speed, we see that it is only the numbers k_n which depend on $\dot{u}$ in (15).

The maximum in the filter output sequence $\{J_j\}$ is obtained by parabolic interpolation between the three highest points. Let j_0 be such that $J_{j_0} = \max\{J_j\}$. The interpolated maximum then occurs at $j_0 + h$, where

$$h = \frac{1}{2}(J_{j_0+1} - J_{j_0-1}) / (2J_{j_0} - J_{j_0-1} - J_{j_0+1}) \quad (17)$$

$$J_{\max} = J_{j_0} + \frac{h}{4}(J_{j_0+1} - J_{j_0-1}) \quad (18)$$

The corresponding transit time is

$$\hat{\tau} = t_0 + (j_0 + h - \frac{1}{2} - \langle k_n \rangle) \Delta t^* \quad (19)$$

The term $-\frac{1}{2}$ is introduced in (19) because it was removed from the definition of filter coefficients, cf. (9) and (16). The term $-\langle k_n \rangle = - (1/\text{NSLIT}) \sum_n k_n$ is necessary because $\sum_n k_n$ may be a non-zero integer (although $\sum_n u_n = 0$ nominally). The resulting transits are effectively referred to a reference line defined by the condition $\sum_n u_n = 0$.

The variance of the estimate $\hat{\tau}$ due to photon statistics can be expressed in the form

$$\sigma_{\hat{\tau}}^2 = A/\hat{a} + B\hat{b}/\hat{a}^2 \quad (20)$$

where the constants A, B are best derived by Monte Carlo method.

4. Process Description

The SM Preprocessing may be executed in steps as follows.

- (i) Read SM Data for one transit (DID19), decompress and compute combined $(B_T + V_T = BV)$ record. Check for overflow and outstanding samples.
- (ii) Get photometric, multiplicity, and other stellar data for the star identified in the SM Data header. Compute an approximate position (α, δ) .
- (iii) Read RT Attitude data for two (or more) points around the expected transit time $t_0 + \frac{1}{2}L\Delta t^*$ ($L =$ record length).
- (iv) Interpolate $(\alpha_z, \delta_z, \omega)$ and $(\dot{\alpha}_z, \dot{\delta}_z, \dot{\omega})$ to $t_0 + \frac{1}{2}L\Delta t^*$ and compute ζ, B_{fgD} , and $\dot{u}$ [eqn (12)].
- (v) Compute $\{k_n\}$ eqn (13) and perform filtering on BV record [eqn (15)].
- (vi) Locate the highest point (j_0) within some confidence interval and interpolate h and J_{max} [eqn (17)-(18)].
- (vii) Compute J_j for $j = j_0, j_0 \pm 1$, and $j_0 \pm w$ separately for B_T and V_T records, and hence h, a , and b for both channels [cf. (8)], and the corresponding mean errors.
- (viii) Consistency checks, e.g.:
 - compare $h(B_T)$ and $h(V_T)$
 - compare $a(B_T)$ or $a(V_T)$ with expected fluxes
 - compare $a(B_T)/a(V_T)$ with expected colour
 - compute residuals and goodness-of-fit

The transit may be rejected or may receive less weight depending on the results of such checks. Also multiplicity information should be regarded. Results may be summarized in a quality index.
- (ix) Output results: $\hat{\tau}, \sigma_\tau, a(B_T), a(V_T), b(B_T), b(V_T), \zeta$ and B_{fgD} . (The destination of the photometric results is as yet undefined, cf. DID22).

DID 19		OUTPUT FROM : SM DATA		PAGE : 1 OF 1					
INPUT TO : SM PREPROCESSING				DATE : 82.12.08					
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG-ITS
ID	-	1. For each SM transit: object identification number	-	0	10 ⁸	0	1	-	8
ISM	-	Star Mapper index	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
IFIELD	(-1) ^f (p8)	field index	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
IGROUP	g (p14)	slit group index	-	1	2	0	1	-	1
TSTART	-	starting time (t ₀)	s	0	2.10 ⁸	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	15
NSMB(K)	N _k [*] (p13)	1.1. For K=1 to L: coded count record, B _T -channel	-	0	255	-	1	-	3
NSMV(K)	N _k [*] (p13)	coded count record, V _T -channel	-	0	255	-	1	-	3
N.B.: L = length of count records (~ 180)									

DID 20		OUTPUT FROM : REAL TIME ATTITUDE INPUT TO : SM PREPROCESSING			PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.12.08			
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC. ABS REL	DIG- ITS
IFRAME	-	1. <u>For each frame:</u> frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1	9
TMID	(p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	15
RAZ	(p6)	Right Ascension of z axis	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	12
DECZ	(p6)	Declination of z axis	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	10^{-9}	10
ARGZ	(p6)	argument of z axis	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	12
DRAZ, DDECZ, DARGZ	$\dot{\alpha}_z, \dot{\delta}_z, \dot{\omega}$	time derivatives of attitude angles	rad/s	-10^{-3}	10^{-3}	-	10^{-11}	9
KFIRST, KLAST	-	if an attitude discontinuity has occurred in the frame, these give the first and last sample affected	-	0	9000	0	1	4

DID 21		OUTPUT FROM : STAR CATALOGUE		PAGE : 1 OF 1					
INPUT TO : SM PREPROCESSING				DATE : 82.12.08					
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS
ID	-	1. <u>For each transiting star:</u> object identification number	-	0	$9 \cdot 10^8$	0	1	-	8
RA ϕ	α_o (p4)	Right Ascension at TEPOCH	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	-	12
DEC ϕ	δ_o (p4)	Declination at TEPOCH	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	10^{-11}	-	12
PMRA	$\mu_\alpha \cos \delta_o$ (p4)	Proper Motion in R.A. at TEPOCH (times $\cos \delta_o$)	rad/s	-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	0	10^{-19}	-	9
PMDEC	μ_δ (p4)	Proper Motion in Dec. at TEPOCH	rad/s	-10^{-11}	10^{-11}	0	10^{-19}	-	9
PX	$\tilde{\omega}$ (p4)	trigonometric parallax	rad	$-5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	0	10^{-11}	-	6
BMAG	-	blue (B) magnitude	mag	-2	15	99	10^{-2}	-	4
BMV, SDBMV	-	colour index (B-V) and s.d.	mag	-1	3	99	10^{-2}	-	4
MULT	-	multiplicity information (TBD)	-	0	9999	0	1	-	4
N.B.: contents identical to DID10 (rev. 1)									

DID 22		OUTPUT FROM : SM PREPROCESSING		PAGE : 1 OF 1					
INPUT TO :		ATTITUDE RECONSTITUTION		DATE : 82.12.08					
DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	NUM ACC ABS	REL	DIG- ITS
ID	-	1. <u>For each SM transit:</u> object identification number	-	0	10 ⁸	0	1	-	8
ISM	-	Star Mapper index	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
IFIELD	(-1) ^f (p8)	field index	-	-1	1	0	1	-	1
IGROUP	g (p14)	slit group index	-	1	2	0	1	-	1
TSTART	-	starting time (t ₀)	-	0	2.10 ⁸	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	15
TAU	τ (p14)	transit time	s	0	2.10 ⁸	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	15
SDTAU	σ _τ (p24)	estimated s.d. of TAU	s	0	1	-	10 ⁻⁶	-	6
ZETAA	ζ (p24)	approximate transverse field coord.	rad	-9.10 ⁻³	9.10 ⁻³	-	10 ⁻⁷	-	5
BFGD(I), I=1,3	B _{fgD} (p24)	array saved for the attitude rec.	-	-10 ³⁸	10 ³⁸	-	-	10 ⁻⁶	6
IQUAL	-	quality index	-	-10 ⁴	10 ⁴	0	1	-	4